

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

UDC 8; 1751

TRANSLATION OF INTERNATIONAL AND THE SO-CALLED INTERNATIONAL WORDS

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Abstract

This paper focuses on the translation of international and the so-called international words in literary translation. There are lots of theoretical arguments in specialized literature which suggest that translation is an impossible task, that it is doomed to failure because languages are never sufficiently similar to express the same realities. We live in a world of globalization and translation has brought people of different cultural and linguistic backgrounds closer together and has built bridges of understanding and appreciation among different societies. Lexical units occupy a considerable place probably in many languages. To them we refer the words which are identical graphically and in some cases semantically in several languages. International words generally appear as borrowings. For example: the following words are understood by the speakers to their international character - *alphabet, atom, barbarism, caravan, economic, electric, element, energy, film, legal*.

Keywords: translation of international words, equivalence, nonequivalence, source language, target language, literal translation

We know that translation is a series of mental thought processes, deliberated or intuitive, and it does not change. Most people know intuitively what translation is, but it is difficult to define or to delimit it. Whilst its aim is to transfer the meaning of a text from one language to another for a similar or different kind of readership as accurately as possible, its success as a full re-statement of meaning is usually only approximate. The difficulties of translating of international words are that very often the inexperienced translators forget the notion of usage and under the influence of familiar graphical form convey the word literally and thus violate the norms of the TL especially in the field of the combinability of words. While the words associated and identified in two languages in the plane of expression do not correspond in the plane of content or in usage or even do not correspond at all. International words can't be translated literally in all the cases. It is admissible when the translator feels that in the given situation the literal translation presents the only correct equivalent of the original. For example: *color correction, bionic computer*.

The purpose of the article is that in the process of translation, there are words belonging to the Azerbaijani language that cannot be translated into another language. Therefore, in the process of translation, these words are required to be translated directly into the target language and explained.

The article contains certain passages from the epos "Koroglu" and the analysis of their translation into English. Koroglu is described as a strong and powerful person in this passage. Unfortunately there is no equivalent of this passage in the Azerbaijani language. Equivalence is always relative, it can be obtained only to some extent as it is influenced by linguistic and cultural factors. The text is situated in its context of culture and the translator does textual analysis, an essential preliminary to translation, and wordings analysis, in order to understand the meanings of individual forms and to

interpret the meaning of the text as a whole. Using the verbs *snatch* and *fling* Khodzko wants to describe Koroglu as a giant.

Arvad dedi:

- *Ay bala, baxıram sənə, nə bilim, vallah. Deməyə də utanıram. Sən elə deyəsən Rüstəm pəhlivansan axı.*

Koroğlu gülüb dedi:

- *Yox, ana, tapa bilmədin.*

- *Onda yəqin Ərəb reyhansan.*

Koroğlu dedi:

- *Yox, yənə tapa bilmədin.*

Arvad bir az fikrə gedib dedi:

- *Onda Giziroğlu Mustafa bəy deyilsən ki?*

Arvad bir duruxdu. Sonra qonağına baxdı.

- *Bala, onda az qalırım. Ay bala, birdən sən o*

Koroğlu olarsan ha.

Koroğlu gülüb dedi:

- *Bax, indi tapmışan.*

The old woman was possessed of uncommon penetration, and was thinking all the time what sort of a man her guest was; she asked him. "My darling son, thou surely be Nazar Djeallaly, from the wandering tribe of the Terdjumans. I conjure thee by God the creator, tell me the truth". "No" "Thou art then Giziroğlu?" "No" "Perchance thou art Reyhan Arab, from the town of Orfah?" "Wrong" "Then surely thou art no other than the chief of the band of Seven Hundred and Seventy seven, the renowned Kurroglou. It is from Chamlybell thou art come from?" "This time you have guessed right, mother".

There is a context and semantic equivalence in both passages. It is wider in A. Khodzko's variant, for example: *Baxıram sənə, nə bilim, vallah – ingilis dilində isə bir qədər başqa şəkildə verilmişdir. The old woman was possessed of uncommon penetration, and was thinking all the time what sort of a man her guest was.*

Use of the grammatical stylistic inversion in English enhances the woman's anxiety. Nazar Jalali

from the tribe Sargadan Terdjuman about whom the woman asks isn't in the Azerbaijani variant: *Koroğlu gördü, yox, arvad bundan yaman qorxub, dedi:*

- *Ay ana, deyəsən, paşalar, tacirlər məni burada çox pis qələmə veriblər, onlar məndən qorxmağa haqlıdır. Çünki mən ki, varam, onların qatiliyəm. Amma da sən məndən niyə qorxursan?*

Tomorrow morning, thou should, go into the street of the bazaar, and proclaim as loud as the lung can bawl, the Kurroglou has arrived here from Cahmlybill, to carry away Princess Nighara, daughter of Sultan Murad, the Turkish Monarch. The tongue of the poor old woman stiffened in her mouth when she had heard these words; she was in a great fright. "Be not afraid, old body". "How can I help not being afraid, old body"; "The reports that circulate here about thee and so dreadful, that if a child cries and the mother desires to silenceit, she tells it, Be quiet, for the wolf is come and is sure to devour the if thou shouldst shriek any longer; the child cries on. The leopard is come; the child continues to cry. But no sooner is it told, Kurroglouis come to fetch it to Chamlybeill, than the child leaves off crying immediately, and being frightened, hides its face in the pillow and falls asleep".

Khodzko uses the phrase "proclaim as loud as thy lung can bowl" in order to enhance the meaning. But if we try to translate it into the Azerbaijani language in order to give its expressiveness completely we'll face problems because adequate translation gives exactly not only the meaning but also the stylistic expressive peculiarity of the original. A translator always faces stylistic problems. It is about the different expressive means that are aimed at the strong emotional impact of the text. For this purpose, both lexical means, stylistic methods and syntactic expressive means must be used. The above – mentioned phrase can be translated as "var qüvvəsi ilə qışqırmaq və ya çıxırmaq". The words "dua yazmaq" in the Azerbaijani variant is quite different in Khodzko's variant [Aleksander Chodzko. 1842]. It is shown that Koroğlu's mother is on her deathbed in the English variant. According to the laws of Moslem religion verses of the Koran must be read in the ear of the person who is on his/her deathbed. "Ölüm yorğan – döşəyi" is given as "on her deathbed" in Khodzko's variant. Both phrases are metaphorical.

Fakky – a person in Turkey who earns money by reading verses of the Koran.

Əfəndim, mənim bir qoca nənəm var. Bir neçə aydı ki, ölüm yorğan-döşəyindədir. Hər nə ələyiriksə, sağalmır. İndi mənə səni deyiblər. Deyirlər ki, sən çox yaxşı dua yazırsan. Gedək mənim nənəmə bir dua yaz!

"My mother is on her death bed, I beg of you to read over the sick woman one chapter of the Koran".

Əfəndi cəld ayağa qalxdı, qələm-davatını götürüb bir əlində imanı, bir əlində tumanı düşdü Koroğlunun yanına. Gəlhagəl gəlib yetişdilər arvadın həyatına. Əfəndi baxdı ki, həyətdə doğrudan da bir qoca arvad var, amma yaman əldə-ayaqdadır. Xörək-zad hazırlayır.

"Pay me for my trouble first". Kurroglou gave him a ducat and they continued to walk together. When they dah entered the court-yard, Kurroglou let the

fakky in before him and the doctor after him. The fakky saw an old woman walking in the court yard.

Surely transformation of the phrase "Əfəndi cəld ayağa qalxdı, qələm-davatını götürüb bir əlində imanı, bir əlində tumanı" into English is very difficult. This phrase reflects the national colouring and it is a form inherent in the Azerbaijani language. It is impossible to find its equivalent. So all such phrases are objective reasons that hinder adequacy: *Koroğlu lap əfəndinin yanına gəlib dedi:*

- *Əfəndi, əgər canına heyfın gəlırsə, çıxart kağız-qələmini, Xotkarın dilindən qızı Nigar xanıma məktub yaz.*

Kurroglou answered: "A miracle! When I left the house she was on the point of death, now she is come to like again. Then I may go?" "Saty, fakky! Take a piece of paper and write down what I shall dictate to thee." The fakky then reached and inkstand from under his girdle, took a leaf, and was ready. Kurroglou said: "Thou must write a letter from Sultan Murad to his daughter Princess Nighara".

A.Khodzko express this passage wider. One should be very careful translating such a combination of words as "On the point of death, a leaf of paper". The denotative meaning of the word *leaf* is *yarpaq* but a *leaf of paper* must be translated into the Azerbaijani as *bir kağız* (some paper):

Dua yazan bir əyri-əyri Koroğlunu üzünə baxıb dedi:

- *Mən hara, Xotkar hara, sən nə danışırsan?*

Koroğlu əlini atıb yapışdı onun biləyindən, dedi:

- *Əfəndi, məni nahaq qana salma! Çıxart kağız-qələmi, yaz!*

"Slay me rather, for I will write no such thing" "How now?" "Thou canst not write then". "I cannot Kurroglou caught him by the throat and squeezeed it so that the fakky's eyes forced from their sockets, and his blackened tongue protruded from his mouth; he was scarcely able to stammer".

Such phrases as *əyri-əyri baxmaq* "scowl", *qana salmaq* are not given in English.

A.Khodzko uses the following words and combinations of words in order to intensify the idea, meaning in English:

Koroğlu başladı deməyə:

- *Xotkarın dilindən qızı Nigara yaz ki, "bu nəməni sənə verən adam mənim çavuşumdur. Mənim barigahımda mənə olan hörmət gərək ona da ola".*

When some parts of the text are not equivalent to each other, but at the same time the translation was made in the appropriate form as a whole. The limits of equivalence should be associated with the subjective approach of the translator, and not with objective necessity. The terms "equivalence" and "translation adequacy" have long been used in translation research, but the boundary between them is not always clearly defined. Often the concept of translation equivalence is interpreted as the adequacy of the translation.

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